

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-EFFICACY AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICS AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENUGU EDUCATION ZONE, OF ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

¹Nkiru Veronica Nwadinobi Ph.D, ²Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu Ph.D, ³Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie Ph.D and ⁴Pat Okoli Ph.D

^{1,2,3}Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State

⁴Institute for Peace, Conflict and Development Studies, Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT)

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Key words:

Self-efficacy, Academic achievement, Mathematics, Public secondary schools, Enugu Education Zone, Nigeria.

Abstract: *This study investigated the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. A correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 3,718 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students from 40 public secondary schools, out of which a sample of 560 students was selected using a multi-stage sampling technique involving simple random and proportional sampling methods. Data were collected using the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995) and students' mathematics achievement scores. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to answer the research questions, while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was employed to test the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics. The findings revealed that a high proportion of students performed poorly in mathematics despite exhibiting high levels of self-efficacy. Furthermore, the result showed a low positive relationship between students' self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics ($r = 0.333$), indicating that self-efficacy had a weak influence on students' mathematics achievement in the study area. The study concluded that self-efficacy alone does not sufficiently explain students' academic performance in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone. It was therefore recommended that stakeholders adopt a comprehensive approach to improving mathematics achievement by addressing instructional, environmental, and other psychological factors alongside self-efficacy.*

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental instrument for national development and individual empowerment, serving as a means through which knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes are transmitted from one generation to another. Education is a deliberate, organized, and systematic lifelong process through which individuals acquire knowledge, skills, competencies, values, attitudes, and behaviour via structured learning experiences (UNESCO, 2024). Education as the vital tool for societal transformation has the school and the teacher therein as the link for the realization of its goals and objectives (Bala & Chigbu, 2021). It involves intentional efforts to facilitate learning and personal development, enabling learners to participate meaningfully in society and adapt to changing environments (Chigbu, Oguzie, Ahaneku & Udefi, 2026). In Nigeria, secondary education occupies a strategic position in the educational system, as it prepares learners for higher education, vocational pursuits, and meaningful participation in society. The effectiveness of secondary education largely depends on students' academic achievement, particularly in core subjects that are critical to scientific and technological advancement.

Mathematics is one of the most important subjects in the secondary school curriculum and is widely regarded as the foundation of science, technology, engineering, and economics. It plays

a vital role in developing logical reasoning, problem-solving ability, and analytical thinking among learners. Consequently, mathematics is compulsory at the basic and secondary education levels in Nigeria and is a prerequisite for admission into many tertiary-level programmes (FME, 2025). The causes of poor performance of students in Mathematics subjects at senior secondary school certificate extermination SSCE in Africa has remained an issue of concern to all stakeholders (Ajagun in Sufiyanu & Sagir 2018). Despite its importance, students' academic achievement in mathematics in public secondary schools has continued to attract concern due to persistent poor performance recorded in both internal and external examinations, including those conducted by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO).

Academic achievement refers to the extent to which students attain educational goals, usually measured through examination scores and continuous assessment. It depicts students' scholastic ability and attainment, which signifies the overall level of knowledge they have acquired in school, a subject or a learning situation (Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu & Ezunu, 2019). While intellectual ability and instructional quality are important determinants of academic achievement, teachers can influence their students' achievements through assigning tasks, evaluative feedback and encouragement (Chigbu, Chukwu & Nwobodo, 2022). Research has

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increasingly shown that psychological factors also play a crucial role in students' learning outcomes. Among these factors, self-efficacy has emerged as a key construct in understanding students' academic behaviour and performance. Proving the above assertion, Schunk, Pintrich and Meece (2008) provided evidence from multiple studies showing that psychological variables such as self-efficacy, goal orientation, and intrinsic motivation significantly affect learning outcomes, beyond cognitive ability and instructional quality.

Self-efficacy, rooted in Bandura's social cognitive theory, is defined as an individual's belief in their capability to successfully perform tasks and achieve desired outcomes (Roslan & Maat, 2019). In mathematics learning, self-efficacy influences students' motivation, level of effort, persistence in the face of difficulty, and emotional responses such as anxiety or confidence (Byiringiro, 2024). Students with high mathematics self-efficacy tend to view challenging tasks as opportunities for growth (Sørli, Malmberg, & Schukajlow, 2024) whereas those with low self-efficacy often perceive mathematics as difficult and may avoid engagement, leading to poor academic outcomes (Zimmerman, 2000).

In the context of public secondary schools in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, students encounter various challenges such as large class sizes, inadequate instructional materials, and limited individualized attention, which may affect both their self-efficacy beliefs and

academic achievement in mathematics. The findings of Odiri (2020) suggest that improving students' self-efficacy beliefs, for example, through supportive teaching strategies or confidence-building interventions can help raise mathematics achievement in senior secondary schools. In contradiction, Sinanan, 2022, insist that the correlation between self-efficacy and mathematics performance was weak and statistically non-significant, suggesting that students' confidence beliefs did not meaningfully influence their mathematics achievement in that setting. This contradicts the common finding that higher self-efficacy predicts better achievement. Self-efficacy determines the emotional, psychological and physical development of adolescents (Chigbu, Obi, Uzoekwe & Akuezuilo, 2021). Although several studies have investigated factors influencing students' performance in mathematics, there is limited empirical evidence focusing specifically on the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement among public secondary school students in this educational zone.

Therefore, this study examines the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable insights for teachers, school counsellors, curriculum planners, and policymakers on the importance of fostering positive self-efficacy beliefs as a

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strategy for improving students' academic achievement in mathematics.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics is a core subject in the Nigerian secondary school curriculum and is essential for students' academic and career development. However, despite the centrality of mathematics, many public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State perform poorly in the subject. Previous studies have attributed low achievement in mathematics to factors such as inadequate instructional resources, poor teaching methods, and large class sizes. While these factors are important, there is growing evidence that psychological factors, particularly students' self-efficacy, play a significant role in influencing learning outcomes. Self-efficacy, which refers to an individual's belief in their ability to successfully complete a task or achieve a goal, has been found to affect students' motivation, persistence, and approach to problem-solving. Students with high self-efficacy are more likely to engage actively in learning, attempt challenging tasks, and persist in the face of difficulty, whereas those with low self-efficacy may avoid effortful learning and give up easily, leading to poor performance.

In the context of the Enugu Education Zone, there is limited empirical evidence examining the extent to which students' self-efficacy influences their academic achievement in mathematics. This gap in knowledge creates uncertainty about whether interventions aimed at improving self-

efficacy could enhance students' performance in mathematics. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone, with the aim of providing insights that could inform educational strategies, teaching practices, and policy formulation in the region.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State.

Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine the self-efficacy scores of public secondary school students in mathematics in Enugu Education Zone.
2. Ascertain the Students' Academic achievement scores in Mathematics.
3. Examine the relationship between students' self-efficacy and their academic achievement in mathematics.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be beneficial to students, parents, teachers, educational administrators, school guidance counsellor, policymakers, and researchers.

The findings of this study will be beneficial to students. It will help them understand the importance of self-efficacy in mathematics learning and how confidence in their abilities can

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enhance motivation, engagement, and academic performance. Students can gain access to the findings through school-based workshops, seminars, or by reviewing summarized reports provided by their teachers.

Parents will gain understanding that challenges in mathematics may arise from mismatched learning styles or low self-confidence rather than lack of effort. This awareness can help parents provide appropriate learning resources, reinforce positive study habits, and collaborate with teachers to support their children effectively. Parents can access the study through school meetings, parent-teacher forums, information leaflets, and community educational seminars.

For teachers, the study will provide insights into instructional strategies that foster students' self-efficacy, such as providing constructive feedback, encouraging problem-solving, and creating mastery experiences in mathematics lessons. Teachers can access the findings through professional development programs, teacher training sessions, educational journals, or school research bulletins.

Educational administrators and policymakers will benefit from the study by gaining evidence-based insights to design programs and policies that support students' psychological and academic development, particularly in improving mathematics performance. They can gain access to the findings through official policy briefs, educational conferences, published

reports, and collaborations with educational research institutions.

The study will equip guidance counsellors with evidence-based insights on the relationship between learning styles, self-efficacy, and mathematics achievement. This information can guide the design of personalized support programs, study skills workshops, and interventions aimed at reducing math anxiety and building academic confidence. Counsellors can access the study through professional seminars, counseling department reports, academic journals, and online research repositories.

Finally, researchers and academics will benefit from the study as it contributes to the existing body of knowledge on the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in the Nigerian educational context. The findings can serve as a foundation for further research. Researchers can access the findings through academic journals, online research repositories, conference proceedings, and citations in future studies.

Methods

This study adopted a correlational survey research design to examine the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone, Enugu State. Correlational survey research design is a design that seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables and the

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direction and magnitude of relationship existing between these variable (Oguzie, Chigbu, Ugwuele & Okpala, 2026). It is employed when the researcher aims to observe relationships naturally occurring among variables. This design is appropriate for this study as the study seeks to examine the relationship between self-efficacy, and academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students in Enugu education zone. The population comprised 3,718 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students from 40 public secondary schools, with SS2 students selected due to their adequate exposure to mathematics content and relative freedom from high-stakes external examinations. A sample of 560 students (15% of the population) was drawn using a multi-stage sampling technique, combining simple random sampling and proportional sampling to ensure fair representation across schools and local government areas.

Data were collected using the General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) by Schwarzer and

Presentation of results

Table 1: Ascertain the Students' Academic achievement scores in Mathematics.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks	
10-19	350	62.5	low	
20-29	150	26.78	Moderate	
30-40	20	3.57	High	
50-69	20	3.57	Good	
70-100		20	3.57	Very good

Table 1 revealed that 350 (62.5%) of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone failed mathematics scoring between 10-19 while 150 (26.78)

Jerusalem (1995) and students' mathematics achievement scores. The GSE is a standardized 10-item instrument with demonstrated validity and reliability ($\alpha = 0.88$) across national and international studies, including Nigerian contexts, and was used without modification.

Permission was obtained from the Enugu Zonal Director of the Post Primary Schools Service Commission, and coordination with school principals and mathematics teachers was conducted prior to data collection.

Data analysis employed descriptive statistics (means, frequencies, percentages) to determine levels of self-efficacy with self-efficacy categorized as low (10–19), moderate (20–29), and high (30–40), and mathematics achievement classified as poor (1–44), fair (45–49), good (50–69), and very good (70–100). Relationships among self-efficacy and academic achievement were analysed using **Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC)**.

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students scored between 20-29 scores, 20 (3.57)

students scored between 10-40, 20 (3.57)

students also scored between 50-69 and 20

students finally scored between 70-100.

Table 2: Determine the level of self-efficacy of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
10-19	20	3.57	low
20-29	40	11.43	Moderate
30-40	40	11.43	High
50-69	160	28.57	Good
70-100	300	53.5	Very good

Table 1 revealed that 300 (62.5%) of public secondary school students has high self-efficacy in the Enugu Education Zone while 160 (28.57) students good self efficacy, 40 (11.43) students

has high self-efficacy scoring between 30-40, 20 (3.57) students has low self efficacy scoring between 10-19.

Table 3: Examine the relationship between students’ self-efficacy and their academic achievement in mathematics.

Source of Achievement(r)	N	Academic	Self-efficacy (r)	Decision
Academic achievement	560	1	0.333	low relationship
Self-efficacy	560	1	0.333	

Table 3 shows that there is low relationship of 0.333 existing between academic achievement and self-efficacy of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone.

Range of scores on the Students' Academic achievement scores in Mathematics.

The findings of the study on the mean of the answers revealed that 350 (62.5%) of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone failed mathematics scoring between 10-19 while 150 (26.78) students scored between 20-29 scores, 20 (3.57) students scored between 10-40, 20 (3.57) students also scored between 50-69 and 20 students finally scored between 70-100. The

Discussion of findings

The findings of this research are based on the following sub-themes:

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study shows that more of the secondary school students flailed mathematics. The present study agrees with the work of Ajagun in Sufiyanu and Sagir (2018) which states that there is high poor performance of students in Mathematics subjects at senior secondary school certificate extermination SSCE in Africa.

Range of scores on self-efficacy of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone.

The findings of the study on the mean of the answers revealed that revealed that 300 (62.5%) of public secondary school students has high self-efficacy in the Enugu Education Zone while 160 (28.57) students have good self-efficacy, 40 (11.43) students has high self-efficacy scoring between 30-40, 20 (3.57) students has low self-efficacy scoring between 10-19. The study shows that more of the secondary school students has high self-efficacy. The present study disagrees with the study of Zimmerman, (2000), which states that those with low self-efficacy often perceive mathematics as difficult and may avoid engagement, leading to poor academic outcomes.

Relationship between students' self-efficacy and their academic achievement in mathematics.

The findings revealed that there is low relationship of 0.333 existing between academic achievement and self-efficacy of public secondary school students in mathematics in the Enugu Education Zone. This means that self-

efficacy does not influence academe achievement in mathematics. The findings disagreed with the findings of (Zimmerman, 2000; Ozuome, Oguzie, Onwukwe & Emeji, 2024) who found that those with low self-efficacy often perceive mathematics as difficult and may avoid engagement, leading to poor academic outcomes. Following the findings there is need to understand other variables which could influence the possible failure in mathematics.

Conclusion

This study examined the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics among public secondary school students in the Enugu Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that a large proportion of students performed poorly in mathematics despite many of them reporting high levels of self-efficacy. This suggests a noticeable disconnect between students' confidence in their mathematical abilities and their actual academic performance.

Furthermore, the study established that the relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in mathematics was low and positive ($r = 0.333$). This indicates that although self-efficacy has some association with students' mathematics achievement, it does not significantly influence performance among the sampled students. Therefore, self-efficacy alone cannot sufficiently explain students' poor achievement in mathematics within the Enugu Education Zone.

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The findings imply that other factors beyond self-efficacy—such as quality of instruction, availability of learning resources, teaching methods, learning environment, curriculum implementation, and students’ study habits—may play a more dominant role in influencing mathematics achievement. Consequently, efforts to improve mathematics performance should not rely solely on enhancing students’ self-efficacy but should adopt a more comprehensive approach that addresses multiple academic and contextual variables.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Mathematics teachers should adopt more effective, student-centred, and activity-based teaching strategies that promote conceptual understanding rather than rote memorization. This may help translate students’ self-confidence into actual academic achievement.
2. Regular training, workshops, and refresher courses should be organized for mathematics teachers to improve their instructional skills, classroom management, and assessment techniques, especially in large class settings.

References

Chigbu, Chukwu, & Nwobodo, (2022). Teacher’s Influence on Scholastic Motivation of Adolescents in Secondary Schools in Enugu State. *Prestige Journal of Counselling Psychology*, 5(2),

3. Government and school administrators should ensure the availability of adequate instructional materials such as textbooks, mathematical instruments, and teaching aids to enhance effective teaching and learning of mathematics.

4. School guidance counsellors should design intervention programmes that address not only self-efficacy but also study skills, test anxiety, motivation, and problem-solving strategies to support students’ overall academic development.

5. Parents should be encouraged to monitor their children’s academic progress, provide a supportive home learning environment, and collaborate with teachers to address learning difficulties in mathematics.

6. Future studies should investigate other psychological, instructional, and environmental variables—such as motivation, learning strategies, teacher effectiveness, classroom climate, and socio-economic factors—that may influence students’ academic achievement in mathematics. Researchers may also consider using mixed-method approaches to gain deeper insights.

Chigbu, E. F., Obi, J. S., Uzoekwe, H. F. & Akuezuilo, J. A. (2021). Self-efficacy as predictor of behaviour improvement among adolescents in Udi Education Zone, Enugu state. *International Journal of*

Nkiru Veronica Nwadinobi Ph.D, Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu Ph.D, Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie Ph.D and Pat Okoli Ph.D

Management, Social Science, Peace and Conflicts Studies, 4(2), 67-76.

Chigbu, Oguzie, Ahaneku & Udefi (2026). Roles of counsellors in mitigating physical and psychological menopausal challenges among women in public hospitals, Enugu State. *MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)*, 3(2), 1-13

Bala, A. S. & Chigbu, E. F. (2021). Perception on the influence of guidance and counselling practices on career Choice among Secondary School Students in Jalingo Metropolis, Taraba State. *Prestige Journal of Education*, 4(2), 274-284. Retrieved from <https://openaccessglobal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/guidance-and-counselling-practice-and-careerchoice.pdf>

Roslan, N. A. & Maat, S. M. (2019). Systematic Literature Review on Secondary School Students' Mathematics Self-Efficacy. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*.

Sørli, K. E., Malmberg, L.E. & Schukajlow, S. (2024). Students' mathematics self-efficacy: a scoping review. *ZDM – Mathematics Education*.

Byiringiro, E. (2024). Mathematics self-efficacy and mathematics achievement in high schools. *Psychology and Education*.

Odiri, E. O (2020), Relationship Between Students' Self-Efficacy and Achievement in Senior Secondary School Mathematics (Delta, Nigeria). *International Journal of Education and Research* (2020).

Oguzie, A. E., Chigbu, E. F., Ugwuele, D. C. & Okpala, M. C. (2026). Academic stress as a correlate of academic achievement among undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. *Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 30-45

Oguzie, A.E., Nwokolo, C., Mokuwelu, O.B. & Ezunu, E.N. (2019). Relationship between secondary school students' study behaviour and their academic achievement in Imo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 3(2), 133-140.

Ozuome, C.C., Oguzie, A.E., Onwukwe, M.C. & Emeji, J.C. (2024). Secondary school students' self-efficacy as correlates of their academic achievement in Imo state. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 8(1), 15-32.

Nkiru Veronica Nwadinobi Ph.D, Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu Ph.D, Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie Ph.D and Pat Okoli Ph.D

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<https://aspjournals.net/Journals/index.php/ajcr/index>

UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning. (2024).
Education: Definition and Key Concepts.
TVETipedia Glossary.

Federal Ministry of Education (Nigeria). (2025).
National Policy on Senior Secondary
Education – Core Subjects List. Federal
Ministry of Education Curriculum
Document.

Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). Self-efficacy: An
essential motive to learn. *Contemporary
Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 82–
91. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1999.1016>

Sinanan, R. (2022). An investigation of
mathematics self-efficacy, the sources of
mathematics self-efficacy, and
mathematics achievement among
primary school students in Trinidad and
Tobago (Doctoral dissertation). Andrews
University.
<https://doi.org/10.32597/dissertations/1774/>

Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R. & Meece, J. L.
(2008). *Motivation in education: Theory,
research, and applications* (3rd ed.).
Pearson.

Schwarzer, R. & Jerusalem, M. (1995).
Generalized self-efficacy scale. In J.
Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston

(Eds.), *Measures in health psychology: A
user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs*
(pp. 35–37). Windsor, UK:
NFER-NELSON.

Sufiyanu H. J., Sagir M. A. & Zainab L. G. (2018).
Causes of Students Mass Failure in
Mathematics at Senior Secondary Schools
Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Some
Selected Secondary Schools in Kebbi State.
*International Journal of Education and
Evaluation* ISSN 2489-0073 Vol. 4 No.4,
www.iiardpub.org.
<https://www.iiardjournals.org/get/IJEE/VOL.%204%20NO.%204%202018/CAU%20SES%20OF%20STUDENTS.pdf>

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